

Dr. BABASAHEB AMBEDKAR'S CONSTITUTIONAL STRUGGLE FOR DEPRESSED CLASSES AND BACKWARD CLASSES

Dr. L. P. Maruthi

Associate Professor, Department of History and Archaeology, Karnatak University, Dharwad, Karnataka

Cite This Article: Dr. L. P. Maruthi, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar's Constitutional Struggle for Depressed Classes and Backward Classes, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 175-177, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The present paper made an attempt to reveal the Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's concern for the depressed people in India. From a very long time i.e. since ancient period the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes as well as Other Backward Classes were depressed by elite classes in Hindu society. They were leading their life as slaves. They had no well status in the society. For the first time Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj took step to giving reservation to them in his state employment to uplift those classes. And he also took step to prevent Untouchability in his state. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar started constitutional struggle for depressed classes to uplift them by socially, politically, economically and educationally. Babasaheb convinced the British Government in respect of the conditions of those people, and he insisted to the Government to provide secular education and reservation in public services. After Indian independence Dr. Ambedkar stood as an emancipator of depressed classes by giving constitutional reservation in political, educational and employment realm.

Key Words: Scheduled Caste, Scheduled Tribes, British, Ambedkar & Constitutional Struggle

Introduction:

From a very long time i.e. since ancient period the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes as well as Other Backward Classes were depressed by elite classes in Hindu society. They were leading their life as slaves. They had no well status in the society. For the first time Chhatrapati Shahu Maharaj took step to giving reservation to them in his state employment to uplift those classes. And he also took step to prevent Untouchability in his state. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar started constitutional struggle for depressed classes to uplift them by socially, politically, economically and educationally. Babasaheb convinced the British Government in respect of the conditions of those people, and he insisted to the Government to provide secular education and reservation in public services. After Indian independence Dr. Ambedkar stood as an emancipator of depressed classes by giving constitutional reservation in political, educational and employment realm.

Methodology:

The present paper consisted explanation and exploration methods. In this study arguments are systematically analysed. For the study, Journals, Books, Constitution of India, Volumes of Constituent Assembly Debates and E-sources etc. are used as both primary and secondary sources.

Objectives:

- ✓ To explore that what was the condition of Depressed and Suppressed people.
- ✓ To reveal the course and consequences of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Struggle for Depressed and suppressed people.
- ✓ To know about the nature of Indian Congress Leaders towards Ambedkar's struggle.

Ambedkar's Constitutional Struggles:

A man can get stable freedom only by the constitutional rights and his all-kind developments (social, political, economic and educational development) also based on those rights only. That is why Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar started constitutional struggles in order to prosper the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes as well as Backward Classes.

Simon Commission and Dr. B. R. Ambedkar:

The Simon commission came to India on February 3rd 1928, to investigate how the India is able to extend parliamentary democracy and to investigating how the reforms of 1919 Act were at working. But there was no Indian in the commission as member. The Congress leaders considered it as a matter of self-respect of Indians, and they decided to boycott the commission. But Dr. Babasaheb met the commission at Delhi, and he tendered some demands of depressed class people before the commission.

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar's some demands as follow. The Government should provide adult franchise to all without discriminating on the basis of tax payers, the person who has huge property. The adult franchise should reach women also without sex discrimination. By the system of adult franchise we can assuage inferiority complex from depressed class people, who were felt we are under the aristocracy of elite class. 22 seats should be reserve for the depressed classes out of 140 seats in Bombay Legislative Assembly. These were the main demands of Dr. Ambedkar. Further as follows:-

- ✓ The British Government didn't proclaim its emphasis on education sector till 1854. The Government was always complied ungenerous policy toward education. Government hasn't done so far an admirable work in the field of education, except ratification of Compulsory Primary Education Bill. The Hunter Commission 1882 recommended to the government that, there should be no discrimination in respect of admission in government school and colleges on the grounds of caste; race etc. although the government doesn't bring the recommendations of Hunter Commission in order strictly. Hereat, the depressed classes remained as illiterates. Some questions have risen towards general franchise, how to give adult franchise to such illiterate people. If the government is responsible to that question, the government should provide education to the people immediately.
- ✓ There should be a representative of Dalits in council of ministers.
- ✓ The Military, Navy and Police departments also should have some reserve posts for Dalits.

Thus Dr. B. R. Ambedkar was caused to indignation of Congress leaders by giving the support to the Simon Commission. But after the proclamation of report of Simon Commission, his thoughts, suggestions and recommendations proved that Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar was a genius and a great nationalist. Dr. Ambedkar was heartily admired by his critics also. Then Dr. Ambedkar became a famous political thinker and great patriot.

Dr. Ambedkar in Round Table Conference:

Simon Commission submitted its report in 1929. According to the report of Simon Commission, the British Government arranged three Round Table Conferences in London from 1930 to 1932 to discuss about the Indian Constitutional reforms. Dr. Ambedkar attended all the three conferences as a representative of Dalits. He made British government to gravitate towards his rhetoric address as a representative of Dalits in the first conference.

In the 2nd Round Table Conference Gandhiji was participated as a leader of Indian National Congress. In this conference Babasaheb insisted the British government to give 'Separate Electorates' to Dalits. But Mahatma Gandhiji opposed the Ambedkar's demand of separate electorates. And he stated that, the Hindu society will split as several communities from the separate electorates. Dalits should be remaining in the Hindu society. They are inseparable part of Hindu society, and he told that I am the real representative of Dalits. Then Ambedkar condemned the statements of Gandhiji that, 'The Congress shows sympathy towards Dalits dramatically, it has not real concern'.

By the effective argument of Ambedkar in second conference Ramsay MacDonald, the British Prime Minister proclaimed the Communal Award on 16th August 1932 in order to giving separate electorates for Dalits. According to the communal award 71 seats were reserved in provincial legislation for Dalits. Due to the proclamation of communal award much suffered Gandhiji started fast unto death in Yerwade jail since 1932 September 20. Rajaji, Rajendra Prasad, Malviya, Kasturba Gandhi etc. were begged Dr. Babasaheb to save Gandhiji's life from his fast unto death, when Gandhiji reached abnormal condition. From that soul-stirring incident Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar agreed to put sign to a treaty which named 'Poona Pact'. According to the Poona Pact 148 seats were reserved for Dalits in provincial legislature instead of 71 separate electorates. The tenure of this reservation was fixed for ten years.

Due to the continuous and hard effort of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, for the first time Dalits got 8.33% reservation in employment at centre.

Conclusion:

If now the people are getting facility of reservation is that the great contribution of Dr. Ambedkar. From 1920 to 1956 Dr. Ambedkar continuously struggled for the rights of women. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar had met the Simon Commission at Delhi, while no one Congress leaders co-operated with the commission. And he convinced the commission to provide the reservation in public services, and political and educational rights. In the same manner Babasaheb attended the all three Round Table Conferences to convince the British Government in respect of political reservation for Dalits, which was most wanted necessity to those people. From the ease less struggle of Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar depressed classes got the 8.33% reservation in employment at centre, on August 1942 for the first time in India. Thus Babasaheb continuously struggled for depressed people until his last breath.

References:

1. Ambedkar B.R., Annihilation of Caste, Publisher- Navyana; 2014.
2. Constitution of India (updated up to Act 2015), (<http://indiacode.nic.in/coiweb/welcome.html>).
3. India: People's forest rights demanding community rights over natural resources, <http://www.cadtm.org/Indiapople-s-forest-right>
4. India; S Forest Rights Act of 2006: Illusion or solution, 15 Dec 2006.
5. J. Cyril Kanmony (Ed.), Dalits and tribes of India, Mittal Publications, 2010.
6. M. L. Mathur, Encyclopaedia of Backward Castes, Vol. 2, Gyan Publishing House, 2004.
7. M.G. Chitkara, Dr. Ambedkar and Social Justice, APH Publishing, 01-Jan-2002.
8. Sanjay Paswan, Pramanshi Jaideva (Ed.), Encyclopaedia of Dalits in India; Leaders, Gyan Publishing House, 2002.

9. Sanjay Paswan, Pramansh iJaideva (Ed.), Encyclopaedia of Dalits in India, Vol. 13, Gyan Publishing House, 2002.
10. The Hindu, 26 May 2016, B. Kolappan, Warrior Tribes who served in Shivaji's Army.